

Forex Market Screener Data Mining

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July 2020

Work Practice Lecture Report

2019/2020

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Universitas Raharja

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.3969220

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Signed: 18 July 2020 / Accepted: 22 July 2020 / Online: 1 Aug 2020

Abstract

Forex Market screener is a one of forex trader's habit. At least 28 currency pairs on every screening which major currency pairs AUD/USD, EUR/USD, GBP/USD, NZDUSD, USDCAD, USD/CHF dan USD/JPY. Leastwise 5 technical indicators mostly used like MA, MACD, RSI, Stochastic dan CCI attached in each 28 pairs charts on certain time frame, to do technical analysis of price change and movement, that generate which currency pairs to trade. However, the fact, traders faced many false signals and miss analysis. One caused by single time frame analysis without comparing others, which less precision, late entry and exit signal, less profit and more loss risk. Data mining might a solution, where mined data would provide current and recent market condition, price change and movement analysis, the most suggestion pairs to trade, all in one dashboard. Forex market screener data mining resulting more precision analysis, early entry and exit signal, more profit and less loss risk.

Keywords: *Data Mining, Foreign Exchange, Technical Analysis, Financial Market*

FOREX MARKET SCREENER DATA MINING

(ENGLISH VERSION)

WORK PRACTICE LECTURE REPORT

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RAHARJA UNIVERSITY

TANGERANG

ACADEMIC YEAR 2019/2020

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Stating that the work of the lecture report is my own work and is not a clone, copy or duplicate of the work study practice that has been used to obtain an Undergraduate degree in both the Raharja University and other universities, and has never been published.

This statement is made with full awareness and a sense of responsibility and willing to accept sanctions if the above statement is not true.

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ABSTRACT

Forex Market screener is a one of forex trader's habit. At least 28 currency pairs on every screening which major currency pairs AUD/USD, EUR/USD, GBP/USD, NZDUSD, USDCAD, USD/CHF dan USD/JPY. Leastwise 5 technical indicators mostly used like MA, MACD, RSI, Stochastic dan CCI attached in each 28 pairs charts on certain time frame, to do technical analysis of price change and movement, that generate which currency pairs to trade. However, the fact, traders faced many false signals and miss analysis. One caused by single time frame analysis without comparing others, which less precision, late entry and exit signal, less profit and more loss risk. Data mining might a solution, where mined data would provide current and recent market condition, price change and movement analysis, the most suggestion pairs to trade, all in one dashboard. Forex market screener data mining resulting more precision analysis, early entry and exit signal, more profit and less loss risk.

Keywords: *Data Mining, Foreign Exchange, Technical Analysis, Financial Market*

FOREWORD

Praise the author to Allah SWT who has made it easy to step and bestows His grace and gifts, so that the Practice Work Lectures Report that the author presents in a simple book. As for writing title of this Practice Work Lecture Report is "[Foreign Exchange Market Screener Data Mining](#)".

The writing of this practice work Lecture report is structured as a condition to complement the lecture curriculum and follow the minithesis. As a writing material, the authors obtain information based on the results of the observation, interviews and literature review from various sources that support the writing of this report.

This little heart also realized that without the guidance and encouragement of all parties the preparation of this Work Practice Lecture Report this will not run as expected. Therefore, on this short occasion, allow the author to give appreciation and gratitude to:

1. Mr. Dr. Po. Abas Sunarya, M.Si as Rector of Raharja University.
2. Mr. Sugeng Santoso, M.Kom as Dean of Faculty of Science and Technology.
3. Mrs. Desy Apriani, S.Kom., M.T.I as Head of Undergraduate Program in Information System.
4. Mr. Oleh Soleh, S.Kom., M.M.S.I Who have guided the author to the completion of this Work Practice Lecture report.
5. Mr. dan Mrs. Lecturer of Raharja University who has given science to the author.
6. Aryanti Muharramah, S.Psi the author's beloved wife, For all encouragement and assistance to the author.
7. Shin Umar Azzaki dan Ahmad Yahya Arif, the author's children over all the spirit given to the author.
8. The beloved parents and family over the prayers for the success of the author.

9. Mr. Suwanto, M.Pd who have contributed thought calculations and equation formulas.
10. Mr. Halim Sugiarto, Director on PT. Topgrowth Futures who has given the author the opportunity to implement the internship to completion.
11. Mr. Dwi Fery, Broker on PT. Topgrowth Futures who has directed the authors during the internship to completion.
12. Partners in Success Trading Group (Suwanto, M.Pd., Junaidi, M.Kom., Harfizar, M.Kom., Nasrudin, Supardi, Supriyanto).
13. Partners in GOLD Trading Group (Dwi Fery, Wahyudi Chandra).
14. Partners in Learn to Trading Group (Ginanjari, Bugi Alfaridi, Muhammad Jalaludin, Nasrudin, Salman Alfarisi).

The authors realized that in the presentation and writing the Work Practice Lecture Report is still a lot of shortcomings and mistakes either in writing, presentation or content. Therefore, the author always receives constructive criticism and suggestions in order to be used as a reference for the author to improve it in the future.

The end of the word, the author thanked for the attention of the reader. May God Almighty give his mercy to all of us. And hopefully the Work Practice Lecture Report can be useful, especially for writers and generally for all readers.

Tangerang, 18 July 2020

[Handy Yulius](#)

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LIST OF SYMBOLS

I. USE CASE DIAGRAM SYMBOL

NO	GAMBAR	NAMA	KETERANGAN
1		<i>Actor</i>	Menspesifikasikan himpunan peran yang pengguna mainkan ketika berinteraksi dengan <i>use case</i> .
2		<i>Dependency</i>	Hubungan dimana perubahan yang terjadi pada suatu elemen mandiri (<i>independent</i>) akan mempengaruhi elemen yang bergantung padanya elemen yang tidak mandiri (<i>independent</i>).
3		<i>Generalization</i>	Hubungan dimana objek anak (<i>descendent</i>) berbagi perilaku dan struktur data dari objek yang ada di atasnya objek induk (<i>ancestor</i>).
4		<i>Include</i>	Menspesifikasikan bahwa <i>use case</i> sumber secara <i>eksplisit</i> .
5		<i>Extend</i>	Menspesifikasikan bahwa <i>use case</i> target memperluas perilaku dari <i>use case</i> sumber pada suatu titik yang diberikan.
6		<i>Association</i>	Apa yang menghubungkan antara objek satu dengan objek lainnya.
7		<i>System</i>	Menspesifikasikan paket yang menampilkan sistem secara terbatas.
8		<i>Use Case</i>	Deskripsi dari urutan aksi-aksi yang ditampilkan sistem yang menghasilkan suatu hasil yang terukur bagi suatu aktor
9		<i>Collaboration</i>	Interaksi aturan-aturan dan elemen lain yang bekerja sama untuk menyediakan perilaku yang lebih besar dari jumlah dan elemen-elemennya (<i>sinergi</i>).
10		<i>Note</i>	Elemen fisik yang eksis saat aplikasi dijalankan dan mencerminkan suatu sumber daya komputasi

Source: <https://widuri.raharja.info/>

II. ACTIVITY DIAGRAM SYMBOL

NO	GAMBAR	NAMA	KETERANGAN
1		<i>Activity</i>	Memperlihatkan bagaimana masing-masing kelas antarmuka saling berinteraksi satu sama lain
2		<i>Action</i>	State dari sistem yang mencerminkan eksekusi dari suatu aksi
3		<i>Initial Node</i>	Bagaimana objek dibentuk atau diawali.
4		<i>Activity Final Node</i>	Bagaimana objek dibentuk dan dihancurkan
5		<i>Fork Node</i>	Satu aliran yang pada tahap tertentu berubah menjadi beberapa aliran

Source: <https://widuri.raharja.info/>

III. SEQUENCE DIAGRAM SYMBOL

NO	GAMBAR	NAMA	KETERANGAN
1		<i>LifeLine</i>	Objek <i>entity</i> , antarmuka yang saling berinteraksi.
2		<i>Message</i>	Spesifikasi dari komunikasi antar objek yang memuat informasi-informasi tentang aktifitas yang terjadi
3		<i>Message</i>	Spesifikasi dari komunikasi antar objek yang memuat informasi-informasi tentang aktifitas yang terjadi

Source: <https://widuri.raharja.info/>

IV. CLASS DIAGRAM SYMBOL

NO	GAMBAR	NAMA	KETERANGAN
1		<i>Generalization</i>	Hubungan dimana objek anak (<i>descendent</i>) berbagi perilaku dan struktur data dari objek yang ada di atasnya objek induk (<i>ancestor</i>).
2		<i>Nary Association</i>	Upaya untuk menghindari asosiasi dengan lebih dari 2 objek.
3		<i>Class</i>	Himpunan dari objek-objek yang berbagi atribut serta operasi yang sama.
4		<i>Collaboration</i>	Deskripsi dari urutan aksi-aksi yang ditampilkan sistem yang menghasilkan suatu hasil yang terukur bagi suatu aktor
5		<i>Realization</i>	Operasi yang benar-benar dilakukan oleh suatu objek.
6		<i>Dependency</i>	Hubungan dimana perubahan yang terjadi pada suatu elemen mandiri (<i>independent</i>) akan mempegaruhi elemen yang bergantung padanya elemen yang tidak mandiri
7		<i>Association</i>	Apa yang menghubungkan antara objek satu dengan objek lainnya

Source: <https://widuri.raharja.info/>

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CHAPTER I

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

Foreign exchange or commonly called Forex, FX or currency markets, is one of the most profitable markets in the financial markets, with the largest liquidity in the world. Operates worldwide, five days a week, 24 hours a day and traded via the Internet (Handayani, Rahardja, Febriyanto, Yulius and Aini, 2019) [2].

Foreign exchange market trade the difference of open price and close price of a currency pair in a certain trading period. Foreign exchange traders will benefit when the price difference is positive for the price movement up, and the price difference is negatively valued in the price movement down, where the reverse of the condition causes a loss.

There are at least eight currencies in the world that are Australian dollar (AUD), Canadian Dollar (CAD), Swiss franc (CHF), Euro (EUR), Pound Sterling (GBP), Japanese yen (JPY), New Zealand Dollar (NZD) and United States dollar (USD), becoming the most widely traded.

Of these eight currencies, there were twenty-eight currency pairs for each exchange rate. Major currency pairs include AUD/USD, EUR/USD, GBP/USD, NZD/USD, USD/CAD, USD/CHF and USD/JPY.

Technical analysis using technical indicators is one of the easiest analysis techniques of foreign exchange market to analyze, measure and predict price movements. Some technical indicators that are widely used for analysis of foreign exchange market include Moving Average (MA),

Moving Average Convergence Divergence (MACD), Relative Strength Index (RSI), Stochastic and Commodity Channel Index (CCI).

Screening of foreign exchange market has become the daily habit of foreign exchange traders. An observation of eight currencies, noting twenty-eight currency pairs, analysis of currency pairs using technical indicators, predicting price movements, and deciding which currency pair to trade on.

With many careful framing, false movements are still found, so analysis errors often occur. One of the frequent errors of analysis is the result of analysis of one trading period only without comparing with another trading period.

Error analysis is the biggest factor that results in the risk of large losses and slight gains.

1.2 Problem Formulation

Based on the explanation above, the author took several issues:

1. Analysis of simpler and more precise foreign exchange market movements.
2. Determine which currency pair to trade on the fly.
3. Greater profit gains with less risk of loss.

1.3 Scope

In order to discuss the problem later becomes more directed and goes well then there needs to be scope and limitation of problems. The scope of the problems that will be discussed in the writing of this Work Practice Lecture Report are:

1. Price analysis data of twenty-eight currency pairs.

2. Price data mining of twenty-eight currency pairs.
3. Data mining of eight currencies.

1.4 Research Objectives and Benefits

1.4.1 Research Objectives

The objectives of the study are:

1. Operational objectives

The operational objective of the study is to know and analyze the constraints on how the foreign exchange trading is currently running.

2. Functional objectives

The functional purpose of this research is that the results of research can be utilized by foreign exchange traders as a basic reference for conducting the foreign exchange market's screening and assisting in decision making of any currency pair to trade.

3. Individual objectives

The individual goal is to add knowledge, experience, introduction and observation of the foreign exchange market at the brokerage department on PT. Topgrowth Futures, so the author conducts research to complete Work Practice Lecture Report.

1.4.2 Benefits of Research

The benefits of this research are:

1. For researchers

To apply the knowledge that has been obtained during education on Raharja University by creating a scientific and systematic research report.

2. For Raharja University

Contributing new references and researches on the application of data mining or data mining in the foreign exchange market.

3. For society

Simplify foreign exchange traders in conducting the foreign exchange market's monitoring, price change and movements analysis, to provide a recommendation of a currency pair to trade, in one container of dashboard.

1.5 Research Methods

1.5.1 Data Collection Methods

As for a more detailed explanation of the methods used by the authors in drafting the Work Practice Lecture Report is as follows:

1. Observation Methods

It is a data collection way in which researchers have no control at all against the observed response of an object, except in determining the observed factor and examining the accuracy of the data. The research was conducted directly in the brokerage department at PT. TOPGROWTH FUTURES which became the research site for obtaining data and information.

2. Literature Review Methods

Literature Review are all efforts undertaken by researchers to obtain and compile any written information relevant to the issue being researched. This information can be obtained from books, research reports, scientific papers, theses/dissertations, encyclopedia, yearbooks, rules, statutes and

other resources. As well as searching the Internet. In this method the author will get the information by studying the books and literature that exist. As well as searching the Internet.

1.5.2 Analysis Method

After the data collection process is conducted through observation and literature review, the existing data will be processed and analyzed in order to get a final result which is beneficial for the research. The Knowledge Discovery in Database (KDD) approach is done in processing the data that has been obtained, one of those processes is Pre-processing. As well as the data mining approach with Classification, Clustering, Association, Regression and Deviation Analysis methods, selected and used in this research.

1.5.3 Designing Method

In designing the system to be created, the design method used is Unified Modelling Language (UML), where the UML diagram used is Use Case Diagram, Activity Diagram, and Sequence diagram, to describe a design of the system you want to build. While the programming language used is MetaQuotes Language 4 (MQL4) based on the C++ programming language in the Metatrader 4 trading platform.

1.5.4 Prototyping Method

To know the initial overview of the system to be created, the need for a prototype method (hereinafter referred to as 'prototyping' method) is a simple model of software creation that allows the user to have an initial or

basic picture of the program and perform an initial test based on the concept of the working model.

Authors use prototyping design, to help design the system to be used, with an Incremental Prototyping approach, or increased prototyping, using a single final product design and a separate built-in component.

1.6 Writing Systematics

In order to understand more clearly this report, the materials listed on The Work Practice Lecture Report are grouped into several sub-chapters with the following delivery systematics:

CHAPTER I INTRODUCTION

It contains about the background, formulation of problems, objectives and benefits of research, scope of research, and writing systematics.

CHAPTER II FOUNDATION THEORY

This chapter contains a theory of understanding and definitions taken from book excerpts relating to the preparation of a thesis report as well as some literature review relating to research.

CHAPTER III DISCUSSION

This chapter contains a brief overview and history of Raharja University, organizational structure, problems faced, alternative problem solving, process analysis, UML (Unified Modelling Language) existing system, as well as alternative problem solving.

CHAPTER IV FINALE

This chapter contains conclusions and suggestions relating to the analysis and optimization of the based systems that have been outlined in previous chapters.

BIBLIOGRAPHY**ATTACHMENTS**

CHAPTER II

FOUNDATION THEORY

To support the creation of this report, it is necessary to put forward the matters or theories pertaining to the problems and scope of the discussion as a cornerstone in the making of this report.

2.1 General Theory

2.1.1 Basic Concept of Foreign Exchange

2.1.1.1 Definition of Foreign Exchange

[Hadi \(1997\)](#) [3] argues that *"Foreign exchange is a foreign currency that has functions as a means of payment in financing every transaction in the international financial economy and has a record of the official exchange rate of the central bank."*

[Joesoef \(2008\)](#) [4] said that *"Foreign exchange is a foreign currency that can be used as a means of payment abroad."*

[Eng, Lees and Mauer \(1998\)](#) [5] Argues that *"Foreign exchange is one type of foreign currency that acts as a financial clerical or acts as an asset in a foreign currency company."*

[Beams, Anthony, Clement and Lowensohn \(2009\)](#) [6] suggested:

There are 3 foreign exchange systems that apply in a country, including the following:

1. Floating Exchange Rate System

Floating rate system no interference from the government has maintained the stability of the exchange rate. This is because the exchange rate is generally determined by the supply and demand for foreign exchange.

2. Fixed Exchange Rate System

In the fixed exchange rate system, the government and the central bank can intervene and also actively involved in the activities of Forex market transactions. By means of buying or selling foreign exchange when the value is not in accordance with predefined standards.

3. Controlled Exchange Rate System

Neither the government nor the central banks of the countries concerned have the exclusive power to determine the value of the available foreign exchange allocation. While the citizens do not have the freedom to intervene in the forex transactions. This is due to Capital Inflows and the export activities of goods that raises the availability of foreign exchange.

2.1.1.2 Definition of Foreign Exchange Market

[Kuncoro \(1996\)](#) [7] explains that all international business activities require the transfer of money from one country to another for example, a U.S. multinational company that established a factory in the UK, at the end of the year the book always wants to transfer profits gained from its business in the UK (in the form of pound) to its head office in the US (in USD) then to convert the currency British pound into U.S. dollars required the forex market.

According to [Madura \(2000\)](#) [8] The forex market is a market that facilitates currency exchanges to facilitate international trade and financial transactions.

[Kuncoro \(1996\)](#) [7] foreign exchange transaction is an exchange of a currency with another currency.

The London and New York session time overlapping between 13:00-18:00 GMT, as well as the Sydney and Tokyo sessions between 00:00-06:00 GMT is a favorite time for foreign exchange trading, where two market sessions will influence each other, and also large volumes of trades are usually traded during this same time. (Handayani et al., 2019) [2].

There are at least eight currencies in the world that are Australian Dollar (AUD), Canadian Dollar (CAD), Swiss Franc (CHF), Euro (EUR), Pound Sterling (GBP), Japanese Yen (JPY), New Zealand Dollar (NZD) and United States Dollar (USD), become the most traded. Of these eight currencies, there were twenty-eight currency pairs for each exchange rate. Major currency pairs include AUD/USD, EUR/USD, GBP/USD, NZDUSD, USDCAD, USD/CHF and USD/JPY.

The foreign exchange market trades the difference in the open price position and the closing price of a certain trading period. There are two types of open positions in the foreign exchange market, i.e. buy positions, when the price tends to rise (price trend rises) and sell position, when the price tends to drop (price trend drops).

Figure 2.2 Trading positions

Two types of price trends in the foreign exchange market, Bull & Bear, where the trend of Bull prices tend to rise and trend in bears, prices are likely to fall. Foreign exchange traders are advised to open a buy position when the Bull trend and sell position on the Bear trend (Handayani et al., 2019) [2].

Figure 2.3 Price trend

In the buy position, it returns a profit when the closing price position is greater than the open price position and will cause a loss when the close price position is lower than the open price position. The opposite of the sell position will be profitable when the price closes lower than the open price and will be lost when the close price is greater than the open price.

To be able to trade on the foreign exchange market, a person or an institution must open a trading account in a foreign exchange brokerage company, then deposit a certain amount of money at the foreign exchange brokerage company which is later used to trade foreign exchange and become a foreign exchange trader (Handayani et al., 2019) [2].

Figure 2.4 Trading flow

Types of foreign exchange brokerage companies include:

1. Dealing Desk (DD) Or broker traders are also called market makers.
2. Non-Dealing Desk (NDD) or a pure broker:
 - a. Straight Through Processing (STP), Direct Line process.

- b. Electronic Communications Networks (ECN), Interbank Market access.

Figure 2.5 Broker type

Source: <https://havetrade.com/>

ECN brokers are the most favorite brokers to open an account, where ECN brokers get information about the foreign exchange market from a consolidated liquidity provider and do not trade against its merchant members (Handayani et al., 2019) [2].

Once foreign exchange traders have an account at the brokerage company of choice, traders can immediately trade using the trading platform provided by the brokerage company. Metatrader 4 is a popular trading platform widely used among brokerage companies.

Figure 2.6 MetaTrader 4 display

Foreign exchange traders will be based on analysis decisions to open and close trading positions. It can be based on Fundamental analysis of Global financial markets issues, or on the other hand using technical analysis that is more dependent on what the analytical indicators are showing about the situation in the past, recent and the prediction of price movements, which are shown on the price chart on the trading platform (Handayani et al., 2019) [2].

Figure 2.7 Market Analysis

Source: <https://medium.com/>

Metatrader 4 is equipped with various analytical indicators for traders to analyze price movements, which are generally grouped as follows (Handayani et al., 2019) [2]:

- Trend: ADX, Bollinger Bands, Envelopes, Ichimoku Kinko Hiyo, Moving Average, Parabolic SAR, Standard Deviation.
- Oscillators: ATR, Bears Power, Bulls Power, CCI, DeMarker, Force Index, MACD, Momentum, OsMA, RSI, RVI, Stochastic, WPR.
- Volumes: A/D, MFI, OBV, Volumes.
- Bill Williams: AC, Alligators, AO, Fractals, Gators, MFI.

The Moving Average (MA) indicator is one of the most widely used indicators to describe price trends and is usually paired with a Moving Average Convergence Divergence (MACD) for measuring strength, reverse direction, or trend area. These two MA and MACD indicators are simple and easy to use indicators as well as powerful analyzers that are widely used. The use of MA and MACD will be faced with the selection of the period and the trading time frame which matches the current market conditions to avoid misanalysis.

Figure 2.8 Technical Indicator examples

The time frame for foreign exchange trading and the selection of the appropriate indicator periods are two combinations that must be fulfilled in analyzing the past price movements to make future predictions of the foreign exchange market. Most traders will use the trading platform's initial setting indicator period based on the market theory they read, or a certain time frame based on what other traders commonly do as mentioned in the articles, while on the other hand, traders also observe another time frames, could be a shorter or longer span of time to follow price movements and market trends.

Figure 2.9 Chart comparison on difference time frame

In conducting foreign exchange market screening, foreign exchange traders will observe at least 28 chart currency pairs, with at least 5 indicators installed, for a single time frame model. And create another model of currency pairs and indicators for different time frame. So, it presented a lot of chart and a lot of analysis models that finally gave too much to be analyzed.

Figure 2.10 Currency Pairs chart display

The analysis generates any currency pairs to trade with. But in fact, despite careful screening, foreign exchange market traders often find false movements and also undergo misanalysis.

2.1.2 Basic Data Warehouse Concepts

2.1.2.1 Data Warehouse Definitions

According to [Hutahaean \(2014\)](#) [12] "*Datawarehouse is a collection of hardware and software components that can be used to get a better analysis of the huge amount of data that can make good decisions*".

[Suraya \(2011\)](#) [13] argues that data warehouse is a database that stores current data and past data coming from various operating systems and other sources (external sources), or an evolutionary process that includes sourcing, storing and providing data that is used to support decision making.

[Widyawati \(2012\)](#) [14] argues that the Data warehouse is a form of databases that have large-scale data. Data Warehouse is not an operational database, but the database containing data in a certain time dimension is very useful for evaluation, analysis and planning done by management in a company.

From some of the above opinion, it can be concluded that Data Warehouse is one form of database for storing large-scale data both now and past data that has been integrated data source and can be used to support decision making.

2.1.2.2 Data Warehouse Benefits

Data Warehouse is usually used for: ([Hutahaean, 2014](#)) [12]

- a. Understand business trends and make better estimates of decisions.
- b. Analyzing information about daily sales and making quick decisions in influencing the company's performance.

2.1.3 Basic Prototype Concept (Prototyping)

According to [Djahir \(2014\)](#) [15], "*Prototype gives ideas for creators and potential users about how the system will function in its full form. The process of generating a prototype is called prototyping*". (hereinafter prototypes would be called prototype or prototyping).

According to [Rosa and Shalahuddin \(2013\)](#) [16], "*The prototype Model can be used to connect a customer's incomprehension on technical terms and clarify the needs of the customer's desired specifications to the software developer*".

So, it can be concluded that the prototype is a model that provides information about how the system works so that customers or users understand without needing to know the technical stuff and clarify the needs of customers want to software developers.

2.1.4 Basic Concept of UML (Unified Modelling Language)

2.1.4.1 Definition of UML (Unified Modelling Language)

In his book, [Yasin \(2012\)](#) [17] expressed UML is the standard language for the writing of blueprint software used for the visualization, specification, formation and documentation of tools of the software system. UML is referred to as a modeling language instead of method. Modeling Language (mostly graphic) is a notation of the methods used to design quickly. Modeling Language is the most important part of the method. UML objectives include:

- a. Provide ready-made models, expressive visual modeling languages to develop systems and that can easily swap models and understand in general.
- b. Provide language modeling that is free of various programming languages and generally understandable.
- c. Bringing together the best practices in modeling.

2.1.4.2 UML Diagram

According to Xu in the Dictionary of Information Science and Technology by [Khosrow-Pour \(2006\)](#) [18], "*UML Diagram: A graphical design notation for communication and understanding*". Which means UML Diagram is a graphical design notation for communication and understanding. Typically, in the UML diagram include activity diagrams, class diagrams, collaboration diagrams, component diagrams, deployment diagrams, Sequence diagrams, state diagrams, and use case diagrams.

On UML 2.3 consists of 13 different diagrams grouped in 3 categories ([Rosa & Shalahuddin, 2013](#)) [16]. The distribution of categories and the various types of diagrams can be seen in the image below:

Figure 2.11 UML 2.3 Diagram

Source: <http://www.uml-diagrams.org/>

Here is a brief explanation of the category's division:

- a. Structure diagrams is a collection of diagrams used to describe a static structure of a system modelled.
- b. Behavior is a collection of diagrams used to describe system behavior or series of changes occurring in a system.
- c. Interaction diagrams is a collection of diagrams used to describe the interaction of systems with other systems and interactions between subsystems on a system.

Because at the writing of this research using 4 UML diagrams including Use Case diagram, Activity diagram, Sequence diagram, and Class diagram, then the diagram described is the 4 diagrams.

a. Use Case Diagram

According to [Yasin \(2012\)](#) [17] The Use case diagram describes the expected functionality of an emphasized system that is "*what*" the system is making and not the "*how*". A Use Case presented an interaction between actors and systems.

b. Activity Diagram

According to [Yasin \(2012\)](#) [17], the Activity diagram describes the various activities in the system that are being designed, how each of them starts, the decision that may occur and how they end. The Activity diagram can also illustrate a parallel process that may occur on some executions.

c. Sequence Diagram

According to [Yasin \(2012\)](#) [17], the Sequence diagram illustrates the interaction between objects in and around the system (including users, displays and so on) in the form of messages that are depicted against time. Sequence diagrams consist of vertical dimensions (time) and horizontal dimensions (related objects). A Sequence diagram is used to describe a scenario or series of steps performed in response to an event to produce a specific output.

d. Class Diagram

According to [Yasin \(2012\)](#) [17], the Class Diagram is a specification that if the instantiation will produce an object and is the core of the object-oriented development and design. The Class Diagram illustrates the structure and description of classes, packages and objects and relationships with each other, such as containment, inheritance, associations, etc.

2.1.5 Basic Concept of Elicitation

2.1.5.1 Definition of Elicitation

According to Sommerville and Sawyer in [Rini, Iqbal, and Astuti \(2016\)](#) [20], *"Elicitation needs is a set of activities that are demonstrated to discover the needs of a system through communication with customers, system users, and other parties who have an interest in system development"*.

According to Siahaan cited by [Dzulhaq, Tullah and Nugraha \(2017\)](#) [21] *"Elicitation is a collection of initial activity needs in engineering needs (Requirements Engineering). Before the need can be analysed, modelled, or completed, the need must be gathered through the elicitation process"*.

According to [Amrullah et al. \(2016\)](#) [22], *"Elicitation is a draft made based on a new system that is desirable by the related management and is denied by the author to be executed"*.

Can be withdrawn from the 3 opinion experts above that this elicitation is the activity that we do aims to find the needs of a system that is needed related parties.

2.1.5.2 Stages of the Elicitation

According to [Prastomo \(2014\)](#) [23], Elicitation obtained through the interview process and conducted through three stages:

1. The phase I Elicitation contains the entire draft of the new system proposed by the management of the parties related to the interview.
2. Phase II elicitation, the result of classifying the first stage of the MDI (Mandatory, Desirable, Inessential) method, the MDI method aims

to separate the design of the system that is important and must be in the system. Here's an explanation of MDI methods:

- a. M on MDI means Mandatory (important). Meaning requirement must be present and should not be eliminated when creating a new system.
 - b. D on MDI means Desirable. The requirement meaning is not very important and can be eliminated, but if the requirement is used in the formation of the system it will make the system more perfect.
 - c. I on MDI means Inessential. The requirement means that the system is not covered by.
3. The phase III Elicitation is a phase II of the elicitation by eliminating all requirement with option I on the MDI method. Furthermore, all remaining requirement are classified back by TOE method, i.e.:
- a. T means technical, meaning how the procedures/techniques of making the requirement in the proposed system.
 - b. O meaning operational, that is how the procedure to use the requirement in a system that will be developed.
 - c. E means economy, the meaning of costs required to build the requirement in the system.

2.2 Specific theory

2.2.1 Knowledge Discovery in Database (KDD)

2.2.1.1 Definition of Knowledge Discovery in Database

Knowledge Discovery in Database (KDD) is the process of determining useful information and patterns that exist in the data. This information is contained in large databases that were previously unknown and potentially beneficial. The term data mining and knowledge discovery in databases are often used interchangeably to explain the process of extracting hidden information in a large database. Actually, both terms have different concepts, but relate to one another. And one of the stages in the whole KDD process is data mining (Nofriansyah, 2014) [24].

2.2.1.2 Process Knowledge Discovery in Database

The KDD process in an outline can be explained as follows:
(Nofriansyah, 2014) [24].

Figure 2.12 Process Knowledge in Database

Source: <https://infovis-wiki.net/>

a. Data Selection

In this process the selection of the data set, creates the target data set, or focuses on a subset of variables (sample data) where the discovery will be performed. The selection results are stored in a separate file from the operational database.

b. Pre-processing and Cleaning Data

Preprocessing and Cleaning Data is done to remove inconsistent data and noise, data duplication, correct data errors, and can be enriched with relevant external Data.

c. Transformation

This process transforms or aggregates the data into a more precise way to process mining by conducting aggregations.

d. Data Mining

Data mining process is the process of finding interesting patterns or information in the selected data using certain techniques, methods or algorithms according to the purpose of the KDD process as a whole.

e. Interpretation/Evaluation

The process for translating patterns generated from data mining. Evaluating (testing) whether a pattern or information is found to be compatible or contrary to previous facts or hypotheses. The knowledge gained from the formed patterns is presented in the form of visualizations.

2.2.2 Basic Data Mining Concepts

2.2.2.1 Data Mining Definitions

Tan in book by [Prasetyo \(2012\)](#) [26] defines data mining as a process for obtaining useful information from large database warehouses. Data mining can also be interpreted as new information extraction extracted from large chunks of data that helps in decision making.

According to Daryl Pregibon in book by [Prasetyo \(2014\)](#) [35][26], *"Data mining is a mixture of statistics, artificial intelligence, and database research"*.

So, based on the opinions above, it can be concluded that data mining is the process of extracting knowledge from large chunks of data to get a new information so it can be useful to help in decision making.

2.2.2.2 Roots of Data Mining Science

If tracked from its root, it turns out that data mining has four fields of science as follows: ([Prasetyo, 2014](#)) [35]

Figure 2.13 Root of Data Mining Science

Source: <https://widuri.raharja.info/>

1. Statistics

This field is the most ancient root, without any statistics then data mining may not exist. By using classic statistics, it turns out that processed data can be summarized in what is commonly known as Exploratory Data Analysis (EDA).

2. Artificial Intelligence (AI)

The AI constricts to information processing techniques based on human reasoning models. One of the AI branches is machine learning, where the computer system is learning with training.

3. Pattern recognition

Actually, data mining is also a derivative of the pattern recognition field, but only processes data from the database. Data extracted from the database to be processed is not in the form of a relationship, but rather in the first normal form so that the data set is formed into the first normal form. However, data mining is characterized by the search of association patterns and sequential patterns.

4. Database system

The root of the fourth field of data mining that provides information in the form of data that will be excavated using data mining methods.

2.2.2.3 Data Mining Type

1. Cluster Detection

There are two approaches to clustering. The first approach is to assume that a number of clusters are already stored in the data, the goal is to break down the data into clusters. Another approach, called Clustering agglomerative, assumes the existence of any number of predefined clusters, each item exists in its own cluster, and the process occurs repeatedly which attempts to merge clusters, although the computing process is the same.

2. Link Analysis

The process of finding and establishing relationships between objects in a data set also characterizes the properties associated with the relationship between two objects. Link Analysis is useful for analytical applications that rely on graph theory to take conclusions. Additionally, Link Analysis is useful for the optimization process.

3. Rule Induction

Extraction of causal rules from data statistic. Identification of the business rules stored in the data. Methods related to induction rules are used for the discovery process. One approach to discovery rules is to use a decision tree.

2.2.2.4 Operation in Data Mining

2.2.2.4.1 Data Mining Process

It was systematically presented by Gorunescu in the book by [Prasetyo \(2014\)](#) [35], there are 3 main steps in data mining including:

1. Exploration / early processing of data

The initial exploration or processing of data consists of data sanitization, data normalization, data transformation, incorrect data handling, dimensional reduction, selection of subset features, and so on.

2. Build models and validate against them

Building models and validating them means conducting various models and selecting models with the best prediction performance. In this step used methods such as classification, regression, cluster analysis, anomaly detection, association analysis, sequential pattern analysis, and so on. In some references, anomaly detection is also included in the exploration step. However, anomaly detection can also be used as a primary algorithm, especially for searching for special data.

3. Implementation

Implementation means applying models to new data to generate an investigative issue estimate/prediction.

2.2.2.5 Data Mining Methods

1. Classification

Classification is the most common method in data mining. Business issues such as Churn Analysis, and Risk Management usually involve the Classification method.

Classification is an action to give groups to each circumstance. Each state contains a group of attributes, one of which is the class attribute. This method needs to find a model that can explain the class attribute as a function of the input attribute.

Data Mining algorithms that require target variables to learn (to get the rules/patterns that apply to the Data) we are standardized with the Supervised Algorithm.

2. Clustering

Clustering is also referred to as segmentation. This method is used to identify the natural group of a case based on a group of attributes, grouping data that has attribute resemblance.

Clustering is the data mining method that Unsupervised, because there is no single attribute used to guide the learning process, so the entire input attribute is treated the same.

Most Clustering algorithms build a model through a series of repetitions and stops when the model has been converged or assembled (the constraints of this segmentation have stabilized).

3. Association

The Association is also referred to as Market Basket Analysis. A typical business problem is analyzing the table of sales transactions and identifying products that are often purchased concurrently by the customer, for example when people buy chili, usually also he buys soy sauce. The similarities that exist from the purchase data are used to identify a group of similarities from what products and habits happen for cross-selling purposes. In the term association, each item is considered informational.

The Association method has two objectives:

- a. To find what products are usually sold together.
- b. To find out what rules are causing the similarity.

4. Regression

The Regression method is similar to the Classification method, which distinguishes it as a Regression method of not being able to search for a pattern that is described as a class.

The regression method aims to have a pattern and define a numerical value.

A simple Linear Line-fitting technique is an example of Regression, where the result is a function to determine the result based on the value of the input.

A more sophisticated form of regression already supports input in a category, so it's not only numeric inputs. The most popular techniques used for regression are linear regression and logistic regression.

Regression is used to solve many business problems – for example, to estimate distribution methods, distribution capacity, seasons and to estimate wind speeds based on temperature, air pressure, and humidity.

5. Deviation Analysis

Deviation Analysis is used to find cases that act very differently than normal. Deviation analysis is very widespread, the most common use of this method is the detection of abuse of credit cards. Identifying abnormal cases among millions of transactions is a very challenging job. Other uses for example, computer network interference detection, production error analysis, etc.

2.2.3 Data Sets

Data sets (datasets) are sets of data that will be processed in the digging of new knowledge and data sets can also be viewed as a collection of data objects. To represent data there are various ways one of them is the use of attributes. Attributes are used to describe types of objects that can be quantitative or qualitative. Data sets can have different characteristics, for example there is a data set that uses a time series value or a numeric value, even an object with a special relationship in it ([Prasetyo, 2012](#)) [26].

The data Set itself is also often a must-do for the preliminary before the information excavation process. Problems that often arise in raw data are data duplication, data inconsistencies, outliers, incorrect data, etc. For this problem, before the data set is processed in the main data mining process, the initial processing of the data becomes important for better data quality.

2.2.4 Preprocessing

Data sets that will be processed by methods in data mining often have to go through the initial work that is entirely separate from the method in data mining. The emergence of initial processing terms or preprocessing is triggered by problems arising in data sets such as too large number of data populations, large amounts of distorted data, too high data dimensions, many attributes or features that do not contribute greatly, and so on. This is why it needs to be done the initial processing on the data set before it is finally released for processing in data mining (Prasetyo, 2012) [26].

Some common work is done as the initial processing on the data set is as follows: (Prasetyo, 2012) [26]

1. Aggregation

Aggregation is a compression of two or more objects into an object.

2. Sampling

Sampling is a commonly used approach for the selection of a subset of objects/data as a whole to be analyzed.

3. Dimensional reduction

Dimensionality reduction is a process of removing or mitigating certain features that it does not have a large contribution to the data set to be analyzed.

4. Binarization and Discretization

Transforming data from continuous type and discrete to binary attributes is called binarization. While data transformation from a continuous attribute to a categorical attribute is called discretization.

5. Feature subset selection

The selection of a feature sub-set is a search process against all possible subsets. In selecting features there are 2 things to note:

a. Redundant features

Duplicate some information or all data information contained in one or more other attributes.

b. Irrelevant features

Features that do not contain useful information for data mining tasks directly.

6. Attribute Transformation

A function which maps the entire set of values of attributes given to a set of new substitutes so that the old values can be identified by one of those new values. One of the functions of the attribute transformation is to standardize and normalize.

2.3 Literature Review

Literature Review conducted to support the observation method that has been done. Of the many previous studies conducted about data mining and foreign exchange trading, in this study took some other research related to this writing, including:

1. Designing and implementing a successful model, with the aim of finding the best formula in the financial market using Data Mining, through the process of obtaining and clearing data, scientific knowledge, limiting the complexity of problems and validating the results correctly (Boetticher, 2006) [27].

2. Overview of application of Data mining techniques such as Decision Tree, Neural Network, Association Rules, Factor Analysis and other in stock market ([Hajizadeh, Ardakani, & Shahrabi, 2010](#)) [28].
3. The use of Data Mining Predictive Modeling with linear regression function in predicting the price of gold accurately, as a reference decision making buy/Sell position in trade, with accuracy 85% ([Priyadi, Santony, & Na'am, 2019](#)) [29].
4. Testing of foreign exchange trend classification using Machine Learning, to predict upward trend and downtrend based on data series, technical analysis at various time frame ([Baasher & Fakhr, 2011](#)) [30].
5. Examination and measuring correlation between performance on validation sets and testing sets using genetic programming system to excavate data on the Ordinance of Foreign exchange trading, directing an understanding of how measurements can increase profits ([Thomas & Sycara, 1999](#)) [31].
6. Data mining techniques have been used to uncover hidden patterns and predict future trends and behaviors in the financial markets. The competitive advantage achieved by data mining includes increased revenue, reduced costs, and a much better responsive and market awareness, by comparing various data mining techniques and discussing the important issues of data mining related in certain financial applications ([Zhang & Zhou, 2004](#)) [32].

7. Data mining techniques, expert systems and computational intelligence to specify tasks and accomplish financial tasks, providing deeper insight into the potential use of intelligent systems on financial markets ([Hi'ovská & Koncz, 2012](#)) [33].

CHAPTER III

DISCUSSION

3.1 Company Overview

Established since 2003, it has now evolved into the best and largest futures brokerage firm in Indonesia that provides facilities and services for transactions of forex, indices and commodities with competitive spreads.

(Source: <https://topgrowthfutures.co.id/>)

Topgrowth Futures operates under official license and is under the supervision of BAPPEBTI, a company that has been legally recognized and has received awards both in terms of legal compliance and financial performance.

Topgrowth Futures provides online trading facilities in the world of foreign exchange and derivatives markets, planning to take advantage of the potential for long-standing Indonesian commodity markets. For Indonesian people who are accustomed to dealing with online trading technology, the sophistication of Topgrowth Online trading platform will be the right partner for investors or customers.

3.1.1 Vision

To be the leading company in the futures trading industry through quality services and innovative work programs, to create an ideal cooperation relationship with customers both in local and global areas.

3.1.2 Mission

- a. Provide the best transaction facilities, with a range of latest and trusted investment products and financial market information services.

- b. Providing online trading facilities for investors in local and global areas through innovative online trading technologies.
- c. Actively participating in building transparent futures trading industry through sustainable education program.
- d. Always improve and develop the quality of professional human resources.

3.1.3 Company Organization Chart

An organization or company must have a structure of the organization used to facilitate coordination and unification of efforts to demonstrate the framework of the relationship between functions, parts, and duties and authorities and responsibilities. PT. Topgrowth Futures has the structure of management organization as follows.

Figure 3.1 PT. Topgrowth Futures Organization Chart

3.1.4 Duties and Responsibilities

PT. Topgrowth Futures in the management structure there are parts that have duties and obligations in completing all its work.

The following are the authority and responsibilities of PT. Topgrowth Futures which are directly related to the observation of the author, as follows:

1. Director
 - a. Responsible for all activities of the company.
 - b. Coordinating with all Departments.
 - c. Supervising the company path.
2. Broker
 - a. Responsible for all activities of Product Brokers.
 - b. Blazing with all brokers.
 - c. Supervise the trades of each Product broker.
 - d. Research & Development of trade volume increase of all brokers.
3. Forex & Gold Broker
 - a. Make daily trading analysis and recommendations Forex & Gold.
 - b. Monitor Customer Trade & Client.
 - c. Research & Development of Forex & Gold Trading Strategy.

3.2 Management of An Existing Workflow

3.2.1 Existing Workflow Procedure

The existing workflow procedure of foreign exchange trading is as follows:

1. Trader Running MetaTrader 4 application.
2. Then open 28 currency charts.
3. To attached at least 5 indicators on each chart.

4. Analysis of rising prices, strong weak movements, trend reversal trends.
5. Choose currency pair to trade on.
6. Open Trading Position.
7. Close trade Positions.

3.2.2 Existing Workflow Analysis on Use Case Diagram

Figure 3.2 Existing workflow Use Case Diagram

Based on the Use Case Diagram image above:

1. 1 application to conduct all foreign exchange trading activities.

2. 1 actor who conducts foreign exchange trading.
3. 6 use case performed by actor.

3.2.3 Existing Workflow Analysis on Activity Diagram

Figure 3.3 Existing workflow Activity Diagram

Based on the Activity Diagram image above:

1. 1 initial node, initiated object.

2. 11 actions, State of the system that executes an action.
3. 4 decision nodes, system options.
4. 1 final node, an object terminated.

3.2.4 Existing Workflow Analysis on Sequence Diagram

Figure 3.4 Existing workflow Sequence Diagram

Based on the image Sequence Diagram there:

1. 1 actor, who conducts foreign exchange trading.
2. 4 Lifeline, participation in interactions.
3. 12 activation, in conducting activities.
4. 24 message, Inter-lifeline communication in interaction.

3.3 Problems and Solving Alternatives

3.3.1 Problems

3.3.1.1 Problem Analysis

Based on the observation and analysis of workflow procedures of foreign exchange trading at PT. Topgrowth Futures, can be accumulated problems that are the following obstacles:

1. The number of currency pairs to be monitored and analyzed.
2. Use of many technical indicators to help analyze.
3. A long set of preliminary analysis preparation, opening 28 currency charts, attaching at least 5 technical indicators on each currency chart.
4. Price analysis series, movements and trends on 28 currency charts.
5. Currency selection process for trading of 28 charts.
6. Still found counterfeit signals and trade direction.
7. Only guided on one chart period only.

3.3.1.2 Workflow Limitation Analysis

The limitation of the foreign exchange market screening workflow is required to centralize the concentrating on achieving simpler workflows and more accurate price analysis. Based on the problem that is in the workflow of the foreign exchange market screening on PT. Topgrowth Futures, the workflow limitation analysis is limited to data mining in the form of:

1. Analysis of price changes 28 currency pairs in a certain period.
2. Average total data excavation trades 28 currency pairs in the hourly period, 4 hourly, daily and monthly.

3. Data mining relationship 28 currency pairs against the currencies.
4. Data mining currency strength against currency pairs.
5. Data mining comparison of currency strength on 9-time frames.

3.3.1.3 Advantages and Disadvantages of Existing Workflows

Results of observation and analysis of workflow procedures foreign exchange market screening at PT. Topgrowth Futures, found advantages and disadvantages as follows:

1. Excess existing workflow is a detailed display of 28 currency charts along with technical indicators used at certain time frame, giving a clear view of price movements and generating simple analysis based on the graphical display.
2. Results of simple analysis as displayed on charts and technical indicators often lead to misanalysis caused by the counterfeit trade direction, which became the lack of existing foreign exchange market screening workflow.

3.3.2 Problem Solving Alternatives

Based on the analysis of the procedures and problems on existing foreign exchange market screening workflow on PT. Topgrowth Futures, proposed alternatives to the problem-solving solutions that are encountered:

1. Using Data Mining methods to generate simpler workflows and more accurate analysis.
2. Dashboard design of data mining visualizations for more accurate analysis and simpler workflows.

3.3.2.1 Proposed Workflows Management

3.3.2.1.1 Proposed Workflow Procedure

1. Collects and calculates the price changes of 28 currency pairs in a certain period and sorted by the largest to smallest currencies price change.
2. Grouping price changes to 28 currency pairs into 8 price change groups with same currency.
3. Calculating the price change of each of the 8 currency unit groups to generate price changes for each currency.
4. Index the currency in the order of the largest price change to the smallest price change based on each currency relationship.
5. Create a currency index comparison table based on 9-time frames.
6. Calculating the overall trade average of 28 currency hourly, 4 hourly, daily and monthly.

3.3.2.1.2 Proposed Workflow Analysis

3.3.2.1.2.1 Proposed Workflow analysis methods

In this research, to analyze data in the application of data mining used processes from the stage of Knowledge Discovery in Databases (KDD) consisting of data selection, pre-processing data, data transformation, data mining, evaluation, and to generate knowledge or knowledge.

3.3.2.1.2.1.1 Data Warehouse

Metatrader 4 provides a complete historical price or History Center that can also be enabled as Data Warehouse, as described earlier.

History Center: EURUSD,H1

Database: 1940 records

Time	Open	High	Low	Close	Volume
2020.07.10 23:00	1.13006	1.13040	1.12950	1.12990	1512
2020.07.10 22:00	1.12983	1.13030	1.12957	1.13006	3045
2020.07.10 21:00	1.13057	1.13058	1.12992	1.12992	2113
2020.07.10 20:00	1.12998	1.13062	1.12954	1.13057	2915
2020.07.10 19:00	1.13168	1.13172	1.12970	1.12998	4045
2020.07.10 18:00	1.13196	1.13202	1.13094	1.13170	4498
2020.07.10 17:00	1.13073	1.13248	1.13016	1.13197	7550
2020.07.10 16:00	1.12932	1.13148	1.12932	1.13074	7430
2020.07.10 15:00	1.12866	1.12942	1.12737	1.12933	5134
2020.07.10 14:00	1.12939	1.13006	1.12852	1.12870	3091
2020.07.10 13:00	1.12911	1.12976	1.12908	1.12940	3532
2020.07.10 12:00	1.12857	1.12950	1.12854	1.12910	5045
2020.07.10 11:00	1.12792	1.12913	1.12781	1.12858	5088
2020.07.10 10:00	1.12651	1.12810	1.12550	1.12791	7035
2020.07.10 09:00	1.12696	1.12728	1.12580	1.12650	4779
2020.07.10 08:00	1.12713	1.12745	1.12632	1.12694	2683
2020.07.10 07:00	1.12745	1.12746	1.12681	1.12712	2097
2020.07.10 06:00	1.12726	1.12750	1.12714	1.12744	2204

Figure 3.5 Historical price

Data Warehouse functions in the price data history or Metatrader 4 History Center used in this study, covering 28 currency pairs.

3.3.2.1.2.1.1.1 Data Mart

History Center also contain more detailed data for each currency pairs, which can be enabled as a Data Mart.

The Data Mart available in History Center includes entities with the following arrangement:

1. Currency pair Name.
 - a. Time Frame.
 - i. Date Time.
 - ii. Open Price.
 - iii. High Price.
 - iv. Low Price.
 - v. Close Price.

vi. Price Volume.

3.3.2.1.2.1.2 Data Processing Scheme

Based on the availability of data that can be compiled from History Center as Data Warehouse with the overall price detail, Data Processing Scheme can be described in this study, as follows:

Figure 3.6 Data processing scheme

3.3.2.1.2.1.2 Data Mining

To support the stages of Knowledge Discovery in Databases used in this study, it can be described the entire flow of data processing stages to generate knowledge, as follows:

Figure 3.7 Data processing stages

3.3.2.1.2.1.3 Data Mining Steps

3.3.2.1.2.1.4 Data Selection

The data obtained in observation analysis procedure is using price data of 28 currency pairs exported from Metatrader 4 application.

The selected data Set is the price data of 28 currency pairs, in certain trading period and contains the following data:

1. 1,209,600 data, trading period per minute, 1 month backward between March 5, 2020 and up to February 5, 2020.
2. 483,840 data, hourly trading period, 3 months backward between March 5, 2020 and up to December 5, 2020.

3. 10,080 data, trading period per 4 hours, 3 months backward between 5 March 2020 to 5 December 2020.
4. 2,520 data, trading period per day, 3 months backward between 5 March 2020 to 5 December 2020.
5. 1,008 data, trading period per month, 3 years back from 5 March 2020 to 5 March 2017.

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G
1	Date	Time	Open	High	Low	Close	Volume
2	2020.03.05	14:11	1.11886	1.11886	1.11884	1.11884	25
3	2020.03.05	14:10	1.11888	1.11897	1.1188	1.11885	63
4	2020.03.05	14:09	1.11892	1.11894	1.11872	1.11889	57
5	2020.03.05	14:08	1.11873	1.11896	1.11873	1.11891	59
6	2020.03.05	14:07	1.11878	1.11893	1.11869	1.11872	82
7	2020.03.05	14:06	1.1186	1.11875	1.11843	1.11875	126
8	2020.03.05	14:05	1.11835	1.11862	1.11818	1.11862	82
9	2020.03.05	14:04	1.11839	1.11842	1.11833	1.11834	41
10	2020.03.05	14:03	1.11845	1.11851	1.11836	1.11838	77
11	2020.03.05	14:02	1.1182	1.1185	1.1182	1.11848	70
12	2020.03.05	14:01	1.11805	1.11822	1.11804	1.11819	47
13	2020.03.05	14:00	1.1183	1.1183	1.11794	1.11807	72
14	2020.03.05	13:59	1.11822	1.11838	1.11822	1.11832	86
15	2020.03.05	13:58	1.11823	1.11827	1.11809	1.11821	93
16	2020.03.05	13:57	1.1182	1.11831	1.1182	1.11822	77
17	2020.03.05	13:56	1.11822	1.1183	1.11816	1.1182	65
18	2020.03.05	13:55	1.11818	1.11828	1.11809	1.11821	83
19	2020.03.05	13:54	1.11824	1.11826	1.11815	1.11816	61
20	2020.03.05	13:53	1.11817	1.11825	1.11815	1.11825	65
21	2020.03.05	13:52	1.11797	1.11826	1.11797	1.11816	79

Figure 3.8 EURUSD 1-minute data sample

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G
1	Date	Time	Open	High	Low	Close	Volume
2	2020.03.06	23:00	1.13059	1.13112	1.12889	1.12901	2195
3	2020.03.06	22:00	1.13177	1.13258	1.13008	1.13061	7504
4	2020.03.06	21:00	1.12985	1.13189	1.12938	1.1318	5207
5	2020.03.06	20:00	1.13055	1.13117	1.12908	1.12985	5485
6	2020.03.06	19:00	1.13194	1.1328	1.12881	1.13054	4730
7	2020.03.06	18:00	1.13102	1.13298	1.13056	1.13193	6367
8	2020.03.06	17:00	1.1349	1.13546	1.12872	1.13103	11834
9	2020.03.06	16:00	1.13227	1.13548	1.13179	1.1349	9302
10	2020.03.06	15:00	1.13162	1.13377	1.13055	1.1323	8412
11	2020.03.06	14:00	1.13322	1.13324	1.13057	1.13163	5777
12	2020.03.06	13:00	1.13165	1.13406	1.13118	1.13325	7499
13	2020.03.06	12:00	1.12939	1.13242	1.1293	1.13164	9213
14	2020.03.06	11:00	1.12724	1.12956	1.12681	1.1294	6529
15	2020.03.06	10:00	1.12343	1.12786	1.1229	1.12723	7383
16	2020.03.06	9:00	1.12282	1.12378	1.12238	1.12344	4570
17	2020.03.06	8:00	1.12284	1.12371	1.12191	1.12283	3091
18	2020.03.06	7:00	1.12308	1.12366	1.12282	1.12285	1539
19	2020.03.06	6:00	1.12336	1.12391	1.12297	1.12309	1707
20	2020.03.06	5:00	1.12318	1.12344	1.12262	1.12337	2207
21	2020.03.06	4:00	1.12457	1.12488	1.12304	1.12321	2991

Figure 3.9 EURUSD 1-hour data sample

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G
1	Date	Time	Open	High	Low	Close	Volume
2	2020.03.06	20:00	1.13055	1.13258	1.12889	1.12901	20391
3	2020.03.06	16:00	1.13227	1.13548	1.12872	1.13054	32233
4	2020.03.06	12:00	1.12939	1.13406	1.1293	1.1323	30901
5	2020.03.06	8:00	1.12284	1.12956	1.12191	1.1294	21573
6	2020.03.06	4:00	1.12457	1.12488	1.12262	1.12285	8444
7	2020.03.06	0:00	1.12366	1.12463	1.12113	1.12454	8920
8	2020.03.05	20:00	1.12141	1.12449	1.1192	1.12366	12939
9	2020.03.05	16:00	1.11869	1.12169	1.11672	1.12139	21266
10	2020.03.05	12:00	1.11734	1.12001	1.11565	1.11868	17893
11	2020.03.05	8:00	1.11347	1.11742	1.11197	1.11734	13713
12	2020.03.05	4:00	1.1137	1.11437	1.1134	1.11346	3500
13	2020.03.05	0:00	1.11323	1.11427	1.11305	1.1137	6508
14	2020.03.04	20:00	1.11235	1.11423	1.11235	1.11333	8311
15	2020.03.04	16:00	1.11254	1.11453	1.10956	1.11237	22746
16	2020.03.04	12:00	1.11568	1.1167	1.11098	1.11254	17883
17	2020.03.04	8:00	1.11569	1.11875	1.11434	1.11567	17613
18	2020.03.04	4:00	1.11665	1.11712	1.11554	1.11568	6413
19	2020.03.04	0:00	1.11721	1.11853	1.11622	1.11665	8687
20	2020.03.03	20:00	1.11591	1.11952	1.11585	1.11715	18315
21	2020.03.03	16:00	1.11192	1.12126	1.11155	1.11588	32189

Figure 3.10 EURUSD 4 hours data sample

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G
1	Date	Time	Open	High	Low	Close	Volume
2	2020.03.06	0:00	1.12366	1.13548	1.12113	1.12901	122462
3	2020.03.05	0:00	1.11323	1.12449	1.11197	1.12366	75819
4	2020.03.04	0:00	1.11721	1.11875	1.10956	1.11333	81653
5	2020.03.03	0:00	1.11334	1.12126	1.10955	1.11715	108883
6	2020.03.02	0:00	1.10428	1.11847	1.10364	1.11333	116195
7	2020.02.28	0:00	1.09994	1.10532	1.09509	1.10275	111808
8	2020.02.27	0:00	1.08803	1.10065	1.08717	1.09997	91486
9	2020.02.26	0:00	1.08805	1.09088	1.0855	1.08803	80648
10	2020.02.25	0:00	1.08518	1.08902	1.08301	1.08805	74443
11	2020.02.24	0:00	1.08183	1.0872	1.08052	1.08527	69416
12	2020.02.21	0:00	1.07846	1.08636	1.07828	1.08482	51554
13	2020.02.20	0:00	1.08044	1.08211	1.07779	1.07847	53476
14	2020.02.19	0:00	1.0791	1.08118	1.07822	1.08046	44050
15	2020.02.18	0:00	1.08351	1.08373	1.07856	1.07912	42858
16	2020.02.17	0:00	1.08398	1.0851	1.08292	1.08348	27102
17	2020.02.14	0:00	1.08409	1.08613	1.08274	1.08295	37686
18	2020.02.13	0:00	1.0873	1.08888	1.08341	1.0841	41677
19	2020.02.12	0:00	1.09149	1.09256	1.08654	1.08731	37969
20	2020.02.11	0:00	1.09107	1.0925	1.08915	1.0915	40642
21	2020.02.10	0:00	1.09438	1.09575	1.09078	1.09108	35893

Figure 3.11 EURUSD daily data sample

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G
1	Date	Time	Open	High	Low	Close	Volume
2	2020.03.01	0:00	1.10428	1.13548	1.10364	1.12901	505019
3	2020.02.01	0:00	1.1094	1.10941	1.07779	1.10275	1044170
4	2020.01.01	0:00	1.12086	1.12245	1.09925	1.10946	983785
5	2019.12.01	0:00	1.10229	1.12391	1.10031	1.12232	957591
6	2019.11.01	0:00	1.11515	1.11754	1.09813	1.10174	963866
7	2019.10.01	0:00	1.08992	1.11792	1.08791	1.11513	1359396
8	2019.09.01	0:00	1.09869	1.11095	1.08846	1.08992	1298732
9	2019.08.01	0:00	1.10767	1.12497	1.09633	1.09899	1829217
10	2019.07.01	0:00	1.13604	1.13711	1.10601	1.10753	1335505
11	2019.06.01	0:00	1.11606	1.1412	1.11602	1.13695	1239558
12	2019.05.01	0:00	1.12114	1.12648	1.11071	1.1168	1230416
13	2019.04.01	0:00	1.12259	1.13238	1.11108	1.12141	1066336
14	2019.03.01	0:00	1.13699	1.14479	1.1176	1.12169	1266478
15	2019.02.01	0:00	1.14458	1.14886	1.12343	1.13707	1180514
16	2019.01.01	0:00	1.1463	1.15697	1.12893	1.14461	1671369
17	2018.12.01	0:00	1.13485	1.14856	1.127	1.14453	1571153
18	2018.11.01	0:00	1.13093	1.14996	1.12154	1.13159	1754171
19	2018.10.01	0:00	1.16174	1.16248	1.13021	1.13103	2078589
20	2018.09.01	0:00	1.15928	1.1815	1.15255	1.16027	1580129
21	2018.08.01	0:00	1.16921	1.17335	1.1301	1.16026	1869923

Figure 3.12 EURUSD monthly data sample

3.3.2.1.2.1.5 Pre-Processing Data

Based on a sample of data from Data Selection, it is still necessary to perform pre-processing Data, to clean up unnecessary data on the next set of processes, reducing data to a smaller data group, integrating data into new data for subsequent processes, transforming data into other forms of data for subsequent processing, discretization data so that it provides other values from a different point of view.

3.3.2.1.2.1.5.1 Data Cleaning

Data cleanup is done to eliminate unnecessary data in the next set of processes.

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G
1	Date	Time	Open	High	Low	Close	Volume
2	2020.03.05	14:11	1.11886	1.11886	1.11884	1.11884	25
3	2020.03.05	14:10	1.11888	1.11897	1.1188	1.11885	63
4	2020.03.05	14:09	1.11892	1.11894	1.11872	1.11889	57
5	2020.03.05	14:08	1.11873	1.11896	1.11873	1.11891	59
6	2020.03.05	14:07	1.11878	1.11893	1.11869	1.11872	82
7	2020.03.05	14:06	1.1186	1.11875	1.11843	1.11875	126
8	2020.03.05	14:05	1.11835	1.11862	1.11818	1.11862	82
9	2020.03.05	14:04	1.11839	1.11842	1.11833	1.11834	41
10	2020.03.05	14:03	1.11845	1.11851	1.11836	1.11838	77
11	2020.03.05	14:02	1.1182	1.1185	1.1182	1.11848	70
12	2020.03.05	14:01	1.11805	1.11822	1.11804	1.11819	47
13	2020.03.05	14:00	1.1183	1.1183	1.11794	1.11807	72
14	2020.03.05	13:59	1.11822	1.11838	1.11822	1.11832	86
15	2020.03.05	13:58	1.11823	1.11827	1.11809	1.11821	93
16	2020.03.05	13:57	1.1182	1.11831	1.1182	1.11822	77
17	2020.03.05	13:56	1.11822	1.1183	1.11816	1.1182	65
18	2020.03.05	13:55	1.11818	1.11828	1.11809	1.11821	83
19	2020.03.05	13:54	1.11824	1.11826	1.11815	1.11816	61
20	2020.03.05	13:53	1.11817	1.11825	1.11815	1.11825	65
21	2020.03.05	13:52	1.11797	1.11826	1.11797	1.11816	79

Figure 3.13 EURUSD 1-minute data sample

In the initial data, there are 5 data elements: Open, High, Low, Close and Volume. While the data to be used in the process series only Close data, so it is done deletion data Open, High, Low and Volume.

	A	B	F
1	Date	Time	Close
2	2020.03.05	14:11	1.11884
3	2020.03.05	14:10	1.11885
4	2020.03.05	14:09	1.11889
5	2020.03.05	14:08	1.11891
6	2020.03.05	14:07	1.11872
7	2020.03.05	14:06	1.11875
8	2020.03.05	14:05	1.11862
9	2020.03.05	14:04	1.11834
10	2020.03.05	14:03	1.11838
11	2020.03.05	14:02	1.11848
12	2020.03.05	14:01	1.11819
13	2020.03.05	14:00	1.11807
14	2020.03.05	13:59	1.11832
15	2020.03.05	13:58	1.11821
16	2020.03.05	13:57	1.11822
17	2020.03.05	13:56	1.1182
18	2020.03.05	13:55	1.11821
19	2020.03.05	13:54	1.11816
20	2020.03.05	13:53	1.11825
21	2020.03.05	13:52	1.11816

Figure 3.14 EURUSD data deletion result

This data cleanup is done on 28 currency pairs, for trading periods per minute, hourly, per 4 hours, per day and per month. So, there is 140 data cleanup steps.

3.3.2.1.2.1.5.2 Data Reduction

Data Reduction is done after Data Cleaning, which serves to parse data into smaller data groups to be used in the next set of processes.

Figure 3.15 USD data reduction scheme

	A	B	C	D	E
1	Pair	TimeFrame	Date	Time	Close
2	AUDUSD	1	2020.03.05	14:10	0.66168
3	EURUSD	1	2020.03.05	14:10	1.11885
4	GBPUSD	1	2020.03.05	14:10	1.29306
5	NZDUSD	1	2020.03.05	14:10	0.63188
6	USDCAD	1	2020.03.05	14:10	1.3419
7	USDCHF	1	2020.03.05	14:10	0.9524
8	USDJPY	1	2020.03.05	14:10	106.883
9	AUDUSD	1	2020.03.05	14:09	0.66163
10	EURUSD	1	2020.03.05	14:09	1.11889
11	GBPUSD	1	2020.03.05	14:09	1.29302
12	NZDUSD	1	2020.03.05	14:09	0.63178
13	USDCAD	1	2020.03.05	14:09	1.34186
14	USDCHF	1	2020.03.05	14:09	0.95239
15	USDJPY	1	2020.03.05	14:09	106.887
16	AUDUSD	1	2020.03.05	14:08	0.6617
17	EURUSD	1	2020.03.05	14:08	1.11891
18	GBPUSD	1	2020.03.05	14:08	1.29306
19	NZDUSD	1	2020.03.05	14:08	0.63181
20	USDCAD	1	2020.03.05	14:08	1.3418
21	USDCHF	1	2020.03.05	14:08	0.95237

Figure 3.16 7 USD currency pairs data reduction result

This data reduction is done on 28 currency pairs, until formed 8 currency consisting of 7 currency pairs respectively. So, there are 49 data reduction sets.

3.3.2.1.2.1.5.3 Data Integration

Data integration is done after Data Reduction, which serves to combine multiple Data Reduction into new data used in the next set of processes.

Figure 3.17 8 Currency groups data integration scheme

	A	B	C	D	E	F
1	Currencies	Pair	TimeFrame	Date	Time	Close
2	USD	AUDUSD	1	2020.03.05	14:10	0.66168
3	USD	EURUSD	1	2020.03.05	14:10	1.11885
4	USD	GBPUSD	1	2020.03.05	14:10	1.29306
5	USD	NZDUSD	1	2020.03.05	14:10	0.63188
6	USD	USDCAD	1	2020.03.05	14:10	1.3419
7	USD	USDCHF	1	2020.03.05	14:10	0.9524
8	USD	USDJPY	1	2020.03.05	14:10	106.883
9	USD	AUDUSD	1	2020.03.05	14:09	0.66163
10	USD	EURUSD	1	2020.03.05	14:09	1.11889
11	USD	GBPUSD	1	2020.03.05	14:09	1.29302
12	USD	NZDUSD	1	2020.03.05	14:09	0.63178
13	USD	USDCAD	1	2020.03.05	14:09	1.34186
14	USD	USDCHF	1	2020.03.05	14:09	0.95239
15	USD	USDJPY	1	2020.03.05	14:09	106.887
16	USD	AUDUSD	1	2020.03.05	14:08	0.6617
17	USD	EURUSD	1	2020.03.05	14:08	1.11891
18	USD	GBPUSD	1	2020.03.05	14:08	1.29306
19	USD	NZDUSD	1	2020.03.05	14:08	0.63181
20	USD	USDCAD	1	2020.03.05	14:08	1.3418
21	USD	USDCHF	1	2020.03.05	14:08	0.95237

Figure 3.18 USD data integration result

This Data Integration is done in 8 currency groups until the currency group is formed. So, there are 8 data integration sets.

3.3.2.1.2.1.5.4 Data Transformation

Data Transformation is done after Data Reduction, which serves to convert multiple Data Reduction into other form data used in next process series.

	SUM()
AUD	100
CAD	200
CHF	300
EUR	400
GBP	500
JPY	600
NZD	700
USD	800

Table 3.1 Currency data transformation format

	A	B	C	D	E
1	Currencies	TimeFrame	Date	Time	Close[0]-Close[60]
2	AUD	1	2020.03.05	14:10	39
3	CAD	1	2020.03.05	14:10	-47
4	CHF	1	2020.03.05	14:10	-53
5	EUR	1	2020.03.05	14:10	50
6	GBP	1	2020.03.05	14:10	104
7	JPY	1	2020.03.05	14:10	-50
8	NZD	1	2020.03.05	14:10	-48
9	USD	1	2020.03.05	14:10	90
10	AUD	1	2020.03.05	14:09	56
11	CAD	1	2020.03.05	14:09	-30
12	CHF	1	2020.03.05	14:09	-36
13	EUR	1	2020.03.05	14:09	67
14	GBP	1	2020.03.05	14:09	121
15	JPY	1	2020.03.05	14:09	-33
16	NZD	1	2020.03.05	14:09	-31
17	USD	1	2020.03.05	14:09	107
18	AUD	1	2020.03.05	14:08	56
19	CAD	1	2020.03.05	14:08	-30
20	CHF	1	2020.03.05	14:08	-36
21	EUR	1	2020.03.05	14:08	67

Figure 3.19 Currencies sum value data transformation result

Data Transformation is done on Data Integration results. Those data converted into sum of calculations tailored to the needs of the next process.

3.3.2.1.2.1.5.5 Data Discretization

Data Discretization is done after Data Transformation, which serves to provide another form of Data Transformation, thereby generating analysis from a different point of view.

	Rank
AUD	1
CAD	2
CHF	3
EUR	4
GBP	5
JPY	6
NZD	7
USD	8

Table 3.2 Currency data discretization format

	A	B	C	D	E	F
1	Currencies	TimeFrame	Date	Time	Close[0]-Close[60]	Indeks
2	GBP	1	2020.03.05	14:10	104	8
3	USD	1	2020.03.05	14:10	90	7
4	EUR	1	2020.03.05	14:10	50	6
5	AUD	1	2020.03.05	14:10	39	5
6	CAD	1	2020.03.05	14:10	-47	4
7	NZD	1	2020.03.05	14:10	-48	3
8	JPY	1	2020.03.05	14:10	-50	2
9	CHF	1	2020.03.05	14:10	-53	1
10	GBP	1	2020.03.05	14:09	121	8
11	USD	1	2020.03.05	14:09	107	7
12	EUR	1	2020.03.05	14:09	67	6
13	AUD	1	2020.03.05	14:09	56	5
14	CAD	1	2020.03.05	14:09	-30	4
15	NZD	1	2020.03.05	14:09	-31	3
16	JPY	1	2020.03.05	14:09	-33	2
17	CHF	1	2020.03.05	14:09	-36	1
18	GBP	1	2020.03.05	14:08	121	8
19	USD	1	2020.03.05	14:08	107	7
20	EUR	1	2020.03.05	14:08	67	6
21	AUD	1	2020.03.05	14:08	56	5
22	CAD	1	2020.03.05	14:08	-30	4
23	NZD	1	2020.03.05	14:08	-31	3
24	JPY	1	2020.03.05	14:08	-33	2
25	CHF	1	2020.03.05	14:08	-36	1

Figure 3.20 Currencies data discretization result

Discretization Data is also done on Data Integration results. Those data is converted into indexes and ratings tailored to the needs of subsequent processes.

3.3.2.1.2.1.6 Dataset Transformation

Dataset Transformation is a format change of the data set from a table form in a Microsoft Excel file to a CSV data format (*Comma Separated Value*). This format change is intended to allow data sets to be processed by MetaQuotes Language 4 (MQL4) programming based on the C++ programming language on the Metatrader 4 trading platform.

3.3.2.1.2.1.7 Data Mining Modeling

Data Mining Modeling process used in the proposed workflow using 5 Data Mining methods are: Classification, Clustering, Association, Regression and Deviation Analysis.

3.3.2.1.2.1.7.1 Classification Model

Classification Model is done to group data based on 2 types of price changes, i.e. rising price changes and falling price changes.

This data obtained from Data Cleaning results of on previous stage with the following calculations:

$$((Close[0] - Close[n]) * Points) > 0 = Price Up$$

$$((Close[0] - Close[n]) * Points) < 0 = Price Down$$

(Equation 3.1)

Description:

Close[0] = Close value of 28 Currency Pairs during screening

Close[n] = Close value n time backward

Points = Conversion decimal Close value to integer

The calculation results are collected in one data group and sorted, from the largest to smallest.

	A	B
1	Currency Pairs	ROC
2	EURUSD	120
3	USDJPY	120
4	AUDNZD	110
5	EURJPY	103
6	CADJPY	91
7	AUDJPY	90
8	CHFJPY	64
9	EURGBP	51
10	GBPJPY	50
11	USDCHF	46
12	GBPNZD	44
13	AUDCHF	43
14	CADCHF	34
15	EURCHF	16
16	AUDUSD	9
17	AUDCAD	8
18	NZDJPY	-2
19	EURUSD	-3
20	GBPCHF	-23
21	USDCAD	-25
22	NZDCHF	-26
23	EURCAD	-35
24	NZDUSD	-53
25	EURAUD	-57
26	GBPUSD	-81
27	NZDCAD	-83
28	GBPCAD	-127
29	GBPAUD	-163

Figure 3.21 Classification Model result

This data group will become material to display on the design of the ROC (Rate of Change) Heatmap in subsequent discussions.

3.3.2.1.2.1.7.2 Clustering Model

Clustering Model is done to separate and group the price data of 28 currency pairs into a cluster with the same currency.

This data is derived from Data Reduction and Data Integration results in the previous step.

Currency Cluster	Currency Pairs						
AUD	AUDCAD	AUDCHF	AUDJPY	AUDNZD	AUDUSD	EURAUD	GBPAUD
CAD	CADCHF	CADJPY	AUDCAD	EURCAD	GBPCAD	NZDCAD	USDCAD
CHF	CHFJPY	AUDCHF	CADCHF	EURCHF	GBPCHF	NZDCHF	USDCHF
EUR	EURAUD	EURCAD	EURCHF	EURGBP	EURJPY	EURNZD	EURUSD
GBP	GBPAUD	GBPCAD	GBPCHF	GBPJPY	GBPNZD	GBPUSD	EURGBP
JPY	AUDJPY	CADJPY	CHFJPY	EURJPY	GBPJPY	NZDJPY	USDJPY
NZD	NZDCAD	NZDCHF	NZDJPY	NZDUSD	AUDNZD	EURNZD	GBPNZD
USD	AUDUSD	EURUSD	GBPUSD	NZDUSD	USDCAD	USDCHF	USDJPY

Figure 3.22 Clustering Model result

This data group will be used as reference for the processing of Association Model and Regression Model in subsequent discussions.

3.3.2.1.2.1.7.3 Association Model

Association Model is done to mix and unite a Clustering Model so that it can be calculated the value of its association.

This data is derived from Data transformation of Clustering Model, by summing up each value of Classification Model's Rate of Change (ROC) for each currency groups in Clustering Model.

Currency Cluster	SUM()
AUD	=SUM(ROC(AUDCAD)+ROC(AUDCHF)+ROC(AUDJPY)+ROC(AUDNZD)+ROC(AUDUSD)+ROC(EURAUD)+ROC(GBPAUD))
CAD	=SUM(ROC(CADCHF)+ROC(CADJPY)+ROC(AUDCAD)+ROC(EURCAD)+ROC(GBPCAD)+ROC(NZDCAD)+ROC(USDCAD))
CHF	=SUM(ROC(CHFJPY)+ROC(AUDCHF)+ROC(CADCHF)+ROC(EURCHF)+ROC(GBPCHF)+ROC(NZDCHF)+ROC(USDCHF))
EUR	=SUM(ROC(EURAUD)+ROC(EURCAD)+ROC(EURCHF)+ROC(EURGBP)+ROC(EURJPY)+ROC(EURNZD)+ROC(EURUSD))
GBP	=SUM(ROC(GBPAUD)+ROC(GBPCAD)+ROC(GBPCHF)+ROC(GBPJPY)+ROC(GBPNZD)+ROC(GBPUSD)+ROC(EURGBP))
JPY	=SUM(ROC(AUDJPY)+ROC(CADJPY)+ROC(CHFJPY)+ROC(EURJPY)+ROC(GBPJPY)+ROC(NZDJPY)+ROC(USDJPY))
NZD	=SUM(ROC(NZDCAD)+ROC(NZDCHF)+ROC(NZDJPY)+ROC(NZDUSD)+ROC(AUDNZD)+ROC(EURNZD)+ROC(GBPNZD))
USD	=SUM(ROC(AUDUSD)+ROC(EURUSD)+ROC(GBPUSD)+ROC(NZDUSD)+ROC(USDCAD)+ROC(USDCHF)+ROC(USDJPY))

Figure 3.23 Association Model calculation

Currency Cluster	SUM(ROC(Currency Pairs))
JPY	516
EUR	195
CHF	154
NZD	110
AUD	40
USD	13
CAD	-137
GBP	-249

Figure 3.24 Association Model result

3.3.2.1.2.1.7.4 Regression Model

Regression Model is performed to provide another value of Association Model, thus generating analysis from a different point of view.

This Data is derived from indexed Association Modelling result based on descending order from largest to smallest.

Currency Cluster	Index(Currencies)
JPY	8
EUR	7
USD	6
CAD	5
CHF	4
NZD	3
AUD	2
GBP	1

Figure 3.25 Regression Model result

This Data will become the material to display on Currencies Strength Detail Prototype Design in subsequent discussions.

3.3.2.1.2.1.7.5 Deviation Analysis Model

Deviation Analysis is performed to demonstrate the fairness of price changes in a particular trading period, making it easier to detect price changes beyond the fairness threshold.

This data is derived from the Data Cleaning process in the previous step, which calculates the average value of the Close value when screening with Close value some period backwards.

Deviation Analysis Model is done to calculate the average value hourly, 4 hourly, daily and monthly.

	A	B
1	00.00	55
2	01.00	70
3	02.00	68
4	03.00	69
5	04.00	57
6	05.00	46
7	06.00	33
8	07.00	41
9	08.00	45
10	09.00	91
11	10.00	97
12	11.00	99
13	12.00	65
14	13.00	75
15	14.00	76
16	15.00	82
17	16.00	100
18	17.00	124
19	18.00	83
20	19.00	57
21	20.00	47
22	21.00	47
23	22.00	45
24	23.00	47

Figure 3.26 Deviation Analysis Model hourly sample

This Data that will become material to display on Average Open Close Detail Prototype design in subsequent discussion.

3.3.2.1.3 Proposed Workflow Design

3.3.2.1.3.1 Proposed Workflow on Use Case Diagram

Figure 3.27 Proposed workflow Use Case Diagram

Based on the Use Case Diagram image above:

1. 1 application to conduct all foreign exchange trading activities.
2. 1 actor who conducts foreign exchange trading.
3. 6 use case performed by actor.

3.3.2.1.3.2 Proposed Workflow on Activity Diagram

Figure 3.28 Proposed workflow Activity Diagram

Based on the Activity Diagram image above:

1. 1 initial node, an object initiated.
2. 13 actions, state of the system that executes an action.
3. 3 decision nodes, system options.
4. 1 final node, an object terminated.

3.3.2.1.3.3 Proposed Workflow on Sequence Diagram

Figure 3.29 Proposes workflow Sequence Diagram

Based on the Sequence Diagram image above:

1. 1 actor, who conducts foreign exchange trading.
2. 4 Lifeline, participation in interactions.
3. 12 activation, in conducting activities.
4. 24 message, Inter-lifeline communication in interaction.

3.3.3 Prototype Design

3.3.3.1 Main Dashboard Prototype

Figure 3.30 Main Dashboard Prototype

3.3.3.2 Currency Strength Detail Dashboard Prototype

Figure 3.31 Currency Strength Detail Dashboard Prototype

3.3.3.3 Multiple Timeframes Currency Strength Detail Dashboard Prototype

	M1	M5	M15	M30	H1	H4	D1	W1	MN
AUD	5	-5	-6	-6	7	7	7	6	-7
CAD	6	4	6	7	6	6	6	-5	3
CHF	4	6	4	5	-5	3	-7	4	7
EUR	-5	3	3	6	3	4	-5	5	3
GBP	-7	-7	-7	-7	-7	-5	3	3	5
JPY	-6	5	5	3	-6	-7	-6	-6	4
NZD	7	-6	-5	-5	5	-6	4	-7	-6
USD	6	7	7	5	4	5	5	7	5
XAG	-8	0	-5	-6	-8	-8	4	-8	8
XAU	-8	8	-5	-6	-8	-8	-4	-8	

Figure 3.32 Multiple Timeframes Currency Strength Detail Dashboard Prototype

3.3.3.4 ROC Heatmap Detail Dashboard Prototype

EURNZD	120	4	-6
USDJPY	120	5	-7
AUDNZD	110	7	-6
EURJPY	103	4	-7
CADJPY	91	6	-7
AUDJPY	90	7	-7
CHFJPY	64	3	-7
EURGBP	51	4	-5
GBPJPY	50	2	-7
USDCHE	46	5	-4
GBPNZD	44	2	-6
AUDCHF	43	7	-4
CADCHF	42	6	-4
EURCHF	34	4	-4
AUDUSD	16	7	-2
AUDCAD	9	7	-1
NZDJPY	8	1	-7
XAGUSD	-2	-8	6
EURUSD	-3	-3	5
GBPCHF	-23	-5	3
USDCAD	-25	-2	6
NZDCHF	-26	-6	3
EURCAD	-35	-3	6
NZDUSD	-53	-6	5
EURAUD	-57	-3	7
GBPUSD	-81	-5	5
NZDCAD	-83	-6	6
GBPCAD	-127	-5	6
GBPAUD	-163	-5	7
XAUUSD	-385	-8	6

Figure 3.33 ROC Heatmap Detail Dashboard Prototype

3.3.3.5 Average Open Close Detail Dashboard Prototype

00:00	55		00:00	117
01:00	70		04:00	80
02:00	68		08:00	169
03:00	69		12:00	141
04:00	57		16:00	177
05:00	46		20:00	79
06:00	33			
07:00	41		MON	376
08:00	45		TUE	387
09:00	91		WED	293
10:00	97		THU	339
11:00	99		FRI	403
12:00	65			
13:00	75		JAN	2310
14:00	76		FEB	1891
15:00	82		MAR	1412
16:00	100		APR	1985
17:00	124		MAY	2264
18:00	83		JUN	2001
19:00	57		JUL	1678
20:00	47		AUG	2268
21:00	47		SEP	1763
22:00	45		OCT	2022
23:00	47		NOV	1779
			DEC	2579

Figure 3.34 Average Open Close Detail Dashboard Prototype

3.3.3.6 Control analysis

To maintain data accuracy in each data processing suite, the activity surveillance tool is required, in this case the activity logging or log file, which can be accessed, which is also useful to find out if there is an error collecting, grouping, calculating, processing and displaying data.

Timestamp	Instrument	Value
2020.07.12 15:10:32.272	my_MarketPerformance5d2 AUDUSD, M15: iClose[581]:107.532, iClose[597]107.54	
2020.07.12 15:10:32.074	my_MarketPerformance5d2 AUDUSD, M15: iClose[372]:1.1768, iClose[388]1.1767	
2020.07.12 15:10:32.074	my_MarketPerformance5d2 AUDUSD, M15: iClose[372]:134.143, iClose[388]134.148	
2020.07.12 15:10:32.074	my_MarketPerformance5d2 AUDUSD, M15: iClose[372]:1.9052, iClose[388]1.9048	
2020.07.12 15:10:32.074	my_MarketPerformance5d2 AUDUSD, M15: iClose[372]:1.2495, iClose[388]1.2493	
2020.07.12 15:10:32.074	my_MarketPerformance5d2 AUDUSD, M15: iClose[372]:0.8879, iClose[388]0.888	
2020.07.12 15:10:32.074	my_MarketPerformance5d2 AUDUSD, M15: iClose[372]:0.6177, iClose[388]0.6177	
2020.07.12 15:10:32.074	my_MarketPerformance5d2 AUDUSD, M15: iClose[372]:70.405, iClose[388]70.42	
2020.07.12 15:10:32.074	my_MarketPerformance5d2 AUDUSD, M15: iClose[372]:0.6558, iClose[388]0.6559	
2020.07.12 15:10:32.074	my_MarketPerformance5d2 AUDUSD, M15: iClose[372]:1.3539, iClose[388]1.3539	
2020.07.12 15:10:32.074	my_MarketPerformance5d2 AUDUSD, M15: iClose[372]:0.9419, iClose[388]0.9419	
2020.07.12 15:10:32.074	my_MarketPerformance5d2 AUDUSD, M15: iClose[372]:107.36, iClose[388]107.375	
2020.07.12 15:10:32.074	my_MarketPerformance5d2 AUDUSD, M15: iClose[373]:0.9444, iClose[389]0.944	
2020.07.12 15:10:32.074	my_MarketPerformance5d2 AUDUSD, M15: iClose[373]:0.6571, iClose[389]0.6569	
2020.07.12 15:10:32.074	my_MarketPerformance5d2 AUDUSD, M15: iClose[373]:74.888, iClose[389]74.854	
2020.07.12 15:10:32.074	my_MarketPerformance5d2 AUDUSD, M15: iClose[373]:1.0639, iClose[389]1.0631	
2020.07.12 15:10:32.074	my_MarketPerformance5d2 AUDUSD, M15: iClose[373]:0.6976, iClose[389]0.6973	
2020.07.12 15:10:32.074	my_MarketPerformance5d2 AUDUSD, M15: iClose[373]:0.6957, iClose[389]0.6958	
2020.07.12 15:10:32.074	my_MarketPerformance5d2 AUDUSD, M15: iClose[373]:79.292, iClose[389]79.29	
2020.07.12 15:10:32.074	my_MarketPerformance5d2 AUDUSD, M15: iClose[373]:113.971, iClose[389]113.947	
2020.07.12 15:10:32.074	my_MarketPerformance5d2 AUDUSD, M15: iClose[373]:1.6215, iClose[389]1.6217	

Too many journal records requested, 16384 first records in list

Figure 3.35 Control Analysis log file

3.3.3.7 System Device Analysis

In order to run Proposed Workflow required minimum specification as follows:

1. Hardware:
 - a. Processor: 2.0 GHz or above
 - b. RAM: 512 MB or above
 - c. Display Resolution: 1024 x 768 or above
 - d. Internet Connection: 56 Kbps or above
2. Software
 - a. Operating System: Windows XP, Vista, 7, 8, 10
 - b. Trading Platform: MetaTrader 4
 - c. Programming Platform: Metaeditor
 - d. Programming Language: MetaQuotes Language 4
 - e. Analysis Platform: Microsoft Excel

3. Brain ware

a. Foreign Exchange Traders

3.4 User Requirement

Based on the observation and analysis of procedures on existing system, there are several needs to draft the proposed system.

The Elicitation method is used to design the needs of the proposed system effectively and efficiently.

3.4.1 Phase I Elicitation

Phase I Elicitation is a list of needs gained from the results of data collection both by means of observation and analysis of procedures. Here is the listed Phase I Elicitation attachment:

Functional	
No	Requirement Analysis
	I want the system can
1	Displaying the whole Dashboard
2	Displaying the Currency Strength chart
3	Displaying Multiple Time Frame Currency Strength table
4	Displaying ROC Heatmap table
5	Displays the Average Open Close per hour table
6	Displays the Average Open Close table per 4 hours
7	Displaying the Average Open Close table per day
8	Displaying the Average Open Close per month table
Non Functional	
No	I want the system can
1	Running in Metatrader 4 application
2	Using the MQL 4 programming language
3	Has an attractive and understandable look
4	Has a responsive look

Table 3.3 Phase I Elicitation

3.4.2 Phase II Elicitation

It is the result of classifying the Phase I Elicitation based on the MDI method. The MDI method aims to separate the design of an important system and should be present in a new system with the design being denied by the author to execute. The following listed Phase II Elicitation attachment:

Functional		M	D	I
No	Requirement Analysis			
	I want the system can			
1	Displaying the whole Dashboard	√		
2	Displaying the Currency Strength chart	√		
3	Displaying Multiple Time Frame Currency Strength table	√		
4	Displaying ROC Heatmap table	√		
5	Displays the Average Open Close per hour table	√		
6	Displays the Average Open Close table per 4 hours	√		
7	Displaying the Average Open Close table per day		√	
8	Displaying the Average Open Close per month table		√	
Non Functional				
No	I want the system can			
1	Running in Metatrader 4 application	√		
2	Using the MQL 4 programming language	√		
3	Has an attractive and understandable look		√	
4	Has a responsive look		√	

Table 3.4 Phase II Elicitation

3.4.3 Phase III Elicitation

It is the result of the depreciation of Phase II Elicitation by eliminating all of the requirement that is the option I in MDI method. Furthermore, all remaining requirement are classified back via the TOE method. The following listed Phase III Elicitation attachment:

Functional		T			O			E		
No	Requirement Analysis	L	M	H	L	M	H	L	M	H
	I want the system can									
1	Displaying the whole Dashboard	√			√					√
2	Displaying the Currency Strength chart	√			√					√
3	Displaying Multiple Time Frame Currency Strength table	√			√					√
4	Displaying ROC Heatmap table	√			√					√
5	Displays the Average Open Close per hour table	√			√				√	
6	Displays the Average Open Close table per 4 hours	√			√				√	
7	Displaying the Average Open Close table per day	√			√				√	
8	Displaying the Average Open Close per month table	√			√				√	
Non Functional										
No	I want the system can									
1	Running in Metatrader 4 application	√			√			√		
2	Using the MQL 4 programming language	√			√			√		
3	Has an attractive and understandable look	√			√			√		
4	Has a responsive look	√			√			√		

Table 3.5 Phase III Elicitation

3.4.4 Final Draft Elicitation

It is the final result of an elicitation process that can be used as the basis for the creation of a system. The following listed Final Draft Elicitation attachment has been made:

Functional	
No	Requirement Analysis
	I want the system can
1	Displaying the whole Dashboard
2	Displaying the Currency Strength chart
3	Displaying Multiple Time Frame Currency Strength table
4	Displaying ROC Heatmap table
5	Displays the Average Open Close per hour table
6	Displays the Average Open Close table per 4 hours
7	Displaying the Average Open Close table per day
8	Displaying the Average Open Close per month table
Non Functional	
No	I want the system can
1	Running in Metatrader 4 application
2	Using the MQL 4 programming language
3	Has an attractive and understandable look
4	Has a responsive look
Compiler,	
(Handy Yulius)	

Table 3.6 Final Draft Elicitation

CHAPTER IV

FINALE

4.1 Conclusion

Based on the results of research and observation that has been done, it can be concluded such as:

1. The use of data Mining using classification Model, Group (Clustering), Association and Regression (Regression) in foreign exchange market screener, provides a simpler and more accurate workflow and analysis.
2. Can avoid misanalysis caused by false signal direction.
3. Facilitate the selection of Currency Pair for trading, based on a Currency that is strengthening or weakening.
4. Providing information of the best time for foreign exchange trading.
5. The Implementation of Dashboard as the result of data Mining, can provide comprehensive information on price movements in the foreign exchange market.

4.2 Advice

The advice that can be given as a consideration material for the PT. Topgrowth Futures brokers and foreign exchange traders, are:

1. Currency selection that is strengthening or weakening is the main factor in the Currency Pair selection that will be traded.
2. Selection of the right trading time, when the foreign exchange market with large volume of trades, can increase the chances of profit and reduce losses.

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